

With the plethora of programming languages these days, and the massive programming information available in the Internet, it can be difficult for a beginner like you to know where to start. When it comes to programming language for beginners, C is an excellent choice. Not only will it educate you of programming fundamentals, this language is also powerful and is widely used in the industry today.

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Here are the reasons why C is a great programming language to begin with:

1. You can't learn Java or C directly.

For you to learn and master C and Java languages, you should have a rock-solid concept of the elements of programming like classes, polymorphism, inheritance, and others. Come to think about it, how will you learn complicated concepts like these if you are not even familiar with the basic elements of computer programming? The language that starts from scratch is C and its foundational concepts are the basis of any other programming concepts we have these days.

2. It is the basis of C , C#, and Java.

C and C# are programming languages based on C. Java also derives its syntax and programming concept from C. This is known as the world's most dominant programming language and it is also derived from C language.

3. Programs that need Object Oriented Programming (OOP) are written in C.

Java, C#, and C employ OOP. Despite being powerful, not all programs use it and those utilizing it are still written in C.

4. C boasts unbeatable performance.

When it comes to speed of execution, C is still unmatched.

5. Most parts of Linux, Windows, and Unix are written in C.

So if you want to program these OS, or if you wish to have your programs run in the said operating systems, better be familiar with C.

6. Drivers of modern gadgets are written in C.

Why is this so? Well simply because C gives users access to the computer's basic elements. It also provides you with direct access to your CPU's memory by means of pointers. You can also use C to control bits and bytes.

7. Mobile phones, PDAs, palmtops and other handheld devices as well as appliance are becoming more popular than ever.

You may not be aware of it, but your handheld devices and home appliances may contain CPU that requires programming and has software dubbed as embedded system programs.

8. Most PC games employ C as their foundation.

No one will be interested in games if it takes too much time for commands to be done. C is used to make things fast and prompt.

9. C is considered as mid-level language.

Programming languages are categorized into three - Low Level, Middle Level, and High Level. Aside from being user-oriented, high level languages also make development of programs fast enough. Machine oriented, low level languages execute programs faster. Middle level languages like C combines the best attributes of the high and low level languages.

10. C is a block-structured language.

This means every code is written in separate block and is not connected with the code in the next block. With this, you can make programming easier and you can minimize the possibilities of unnecessary side effects.

With the above-mentioned reasons, do you still have doubts why C is the best computer programming language for beginners?

The Server Server server is in fact responsible for providing Web pages based on the client's needs and demands on the Internet, which can be done both statically (as well as dynamically).

Server-side scripting Today, in web programming, most companies and designers work in this area. Server-side programming has a major difference with the user's programming, which is to focus on server-side programming on Behind the scenes and site communications with databases and databases, but programming side-by-side... In the meantime, ASP.NET, Python, C #, Java languages are among these types of programming, and in the top of these languages, the language Powerful PHP.

User-Programming In this section, webdesigners (page designers) dominate this domain, which is roughly the opposite of user-side programming, this section focuses on visual factors. The most [code language converter online](#)

well-known languages, HTML and CSS languages We will discuss further languages ??in the remainder of this article. Simply put, the structure and organization of the pages of the site with HTML and its details, such as the type of post, fonts, colors, and the like of the attributes by CSS is defined; in other words, the HTML builds the page and then the CSS is mounted on it and sets out more details. Another case we can mention is the JAVA Script language Functions such as the keystroke response or mouse control and the interactive performance of the website are used by Java Script. This language is run only by the browser.

Server-side and user-side mechanism:

HTML HTML is a layout and raw shell of a website. The elements of the page are titles, headings, text and links toHTML. This standard markup language is one of the major cores on the Internet and can be called the backbone of all web pages. HTML5 is the latest version of HTML that has been published and is a dynamic language; this means it can create beautiful little code with little coding.

CSS CSS is a language in which users can specify the style and format of the pages and tabs of the website. If theCSS comes with HTML, it allows the developer to define pages with different formats and appearance on a site. Colors, layers and fonts are stored in a specified file that is separate from the core code of the web page. These two languages ??provide the basic structure and style information for building a static page (a static page is a

page that will be displayed to all visitors with each device and browser in one form). Now many web pages are dynamic. The dynamic page is designed, many site users today do not welcome static sites. To create more complex pages, you need to use advanced server-side and client-side scripts.

JavaScript JavaScript is a programming language that brings animation, games, apps, interactions and other interactive content to the site and brings the site to life. After the HTML and CSS, JavaScript is most used among user-side scripts. Some JavaScript software can even run without communication with the web server, which means that these codes and sites that use this language are able to work without even connecting to the Internet.

PHP accounts for over 75% of web servers using PHP. PHP is a comprehensive programming language for the server. The importance and advantage of PHP is open source, or the so-called open source; it also has the language of the program. Writing on the Internet level has a great community of support and answers to questions and bugs. PHP is compatible with various operating systems. The Arvin Karen website design company is capable of designing powerful and professional websites. The vast language was born in 2004, and now more than 200 million websites worldwide are redesigned and developed by PHP. Websites such as Facebook and WordPress use this platform. PHP is a scripting language that is usually interpreted and interpreted by an interpreter. For this reason, this language is suitable for server-side programming, since it easily covers the tasks and tasks of the server that are repeatedly executed. And they do them. Here are some other points about this language:

Python Python is a high-level, high-level programming language that puts its emphasis on readable code. For web developers, it means they are dealing with fewer lines of code than other popular languages. Python does this through a large standard library, which keeps the actual code short and simple. This library is a file that contains pre-written pragmatic code that is provided by community members for the evolution of Python. And can be downloaded and used by these libraries when needed. Like Java, Python is designed for web servers with high traffic volume. Yahoo Maps is an example of sites that use Python.